
Research

A Robust Direct Torque and Flux Based Design Twisting Mode Control for SRM Control

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Abstract: The switched reluctance motor (SRM) has many exceptional qualities. How to manage the torque ripple, however, to expand its use and popularity, is a hot topic in academia. The switched reluctance motor's conventional direct torque control (DTC) using PI can somewhat reduce the torque ripple, but its control is quite constrained. Significant overshoot and inadequate robustness are additional problems. In this paper, the Twisting Mode Direct Torque Controller and a few improvements are added to our DTC are used to control the SRM. Finally, the theory was modeled and validated using MATLAB/Simulink. The findings show that the switched reluctance motor's DTC based on sliding mode control successfully improves the system's control performance, reduces torque ripple, and satisfies control requirements when compared to the Classic direct torque control.

Keywords: Switched Reluctance Motor (SRM), DTC, Sliding mode control, Twisting controller

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Introduction

Emelyanov and other Soviet academics first suggested and developed Variable Structure Control (VSC) combining Sliding Mode Control (SMC) in the early 1950s; by the end of the 1970s, it had gained recognition as one of the most effective robust control approaches. The control research community has developed a sizeable interest in VSC and SMC over the past two decades [1].

The nonlinear control method known as sliding mode control (SMC) is notable for its accuracy, resilience, and simplicity of tuning and application. A specific surface in the state space, referred to as the sliding surface, is where SMS systems are intended to drive the system states. Sliding mode control maintains the states in the immediate vicinity of the sliding surface once the sliding surface is reached. As a result, the sliding mode controller has a two-part design. The first step entails designing a sliding surface so that the motion complies with design requirements. The second is involved with choosing a control law that will attract the system state's attention to the switching surface [2].

The sliding mode control has two major advantages. The system's dynamic behavior can first be modified by selecting a certain sliding function. Second, few specific uncertainties have zero effect on the closed loop response. This idea encompasses bounded nonlinearity, disruption, and model parameter uncertainty. Practically speaking, SMC enables the control of nonlinear processes that are exposed to outside shocks and significant model uncertainty [2,3,4].

The traditional sliding-mode control has a chattering issue by nature. The usage of High Order Sliding Mode is one of the strategies for chattering reduction that have been discussed in the literature.

High-order SM techniques have the main advantage over first-order approaches in that they lessen the chattering phenomena, which primarily disturbs the control inputs and subsequently can harm the actuators of the controlled system.

Thus, the design of the sliding mode controller (SMC) of SRM is the subject of this chapter. To start, the (SMC) design processes were clearly outlined. We suggest the design of a Twisting algorithm controller (TC) for SRM speed management to lessen phenomenon chattering. The outcomes of the simulation will support this insertion.

2. Sliding Mode Control

2.1. Bases of sliding mode control theory

A system with changeable structure is one whose structure varies while it is in use. It can be identified by the switching logic used. With this option, the system is able to change between structures at any time and may have new properties that may not apply to all structures. The state trajectory is driven to a surface in the sliding mode control and then, using the switching law, it is compelled to remain close to this surface, which is referred to as the sliding surface and also the movements that take place as sliding motions [5].

There are three separate sections to the trajectory in the phase plane:

- Reaching phase or convergence mode: is the mode in which the variable to be modified tends toward the switching surface $S(x_1, x_2) = 0$ from any initial point in the phase plane (x_1, x_2) . The convergence criterion and a discontinuous control law describe this mode.
- The sliding mode (SM): is the mode where the state variable approaches the sliding surface as well as moves closer to the phase plane's origin. The selection of the sliding surface $S(x_1, x_2) = 0$ defines the dynamics of this mode.
- The steady state mode (SSM): This mode, which is introduced for the study of the system's reaction at its equilibrium point, is distinguished by the effectiveness and efficiency of the control.

Figure 01: Different modes for the trajectory in the phase plane.

2.2. Synthesis of the control law

This control method involves changing the dynamic system's structural behavior using discontinuous functions so that the state vector x moves along the trajectory $S(x) = 0$ in the state space.

The command by sliding mode is synthesized in three steps:

- Choice of sliding surface.

- Establishing the convergence condition.
- Find the control law that enables access to and habitation of the surface.

2.3. Chattering phenomenon

Engineers may encounter the unfavorable phenomena of oscillations with finite frequency and amplitude, or "chattering," in real world applications of sliding mode control (figure 02). Because chattering causes high wear on moving mechanical parts, low control accuracy, and massive heat losses in power circuits, it is a detrimental occurrence. Actuator constraints or control-level switching delays are the main causes of this phenomena. [6]

Figure 02: The chattering phenomenon.

Many solutions have been put up to lessen or completely eradicate this issue, including the boundary layer solution, fuzzy sliding mode, higher order sliding mode (which is the proposed one in this work), approach law... [7]

3. High Order Sliding Mode Control

For a variety of control issues with uncertainty, classic sliding modes offer reliable, high-accuracy solutions. There are still two primary limitations, though. First, the constraint must be of relative degree 1, meaning that the control must explicitly exist in the constraint's first-time derivative in order for it to be held at zero in typical sliding modes. Hence, finding a suitable constraint is necessary. If the control has any physical sensation, high-frequency control switching may quickly result in intolerable practical issues (chattering effect).

Assume that the control only affects the sliding variable \ddot{s} and that the problem is to maintain s at zero. Most frequently, the constraint function $\sigma = s + s'$ is used. By design, the control is contained in the expression $\dot{\sigma} = \ddot{s} + s''$, and can be kept at zero in a standard sliding mod Hence, s tends asymptotically to zero. It is not possible to maintain it at exactly zero. To actualize this scheme, one must additionally compute s' . The second-order sliding mode method can achieve both of these objectives, exact robust differentiation and precisely maintaining $s = 0$.

Assume that the control is already present in s' and the problem is to keep s at zero. This issue can be simply resolved using standard sliding modes. Yet, the chattering effect frequently renders the solution unsatisfactory. Consider the control derivative as a new virtual control as a potential remedy. When the aforementioned logic is implemented, a second-order sliding mode technique is used to complete the work precisely and in a finite amount of time using continuous control. Thus, it is to be anticipated that the chattering effect is much reduced.

3.1. Sliding Mode Controllers

Think of a dynamical system of the following:

$$\dot{x} = f(t, x) + g(t, x)u \tag{1}$$

u : The system entry.

x : system state.

By requiring the state trajectories of the system to evolve after a finite amount of time on the set $s = 0$ and not to depart from it subsequently, the goal is to produce a sliding regime of order two with respect to s [8]:

$$s = \dot{s} = 0 \tag{2}$$

This is accomplished by a command operating on the sliding variable's second derivative, which, generally, can be expressed as follows:

$$\ddot{s} = \varphi(x, t) + \Phi(x, t)u \tag{3}$$

To evaluate the boundness of the variable \ddot{s} and the reachability of the sliding surface, it is important to test the following working hypothesis before implementing sliding mode algorithms of order two:

- the functions $\varphi(x, t)$ and $\Phi(x, t)$ are some unknown smooth functions.
- S_0, C_0, K_m and K_M are four positive constants which in neighborhood $|s(x, t)| < S_0$, then, the inequalities hold:

$$|\varphi(x, t)| < C_0 \text{ and } 0 < K_m \leq \Phi(x, t) \leq K_M$$

According to the aforementioned hypotheses, for the input under consideration, the 2nd derivative of the switching function is uniformly bounded in a particular domain.

We can write that any solution to equation $e = x - x_d$ meets the following differential inclusion by adhering to the predefined conditions:

$$\ddot{s} \in [-C_0, C_0] + [K_m, K_M] \cdot u \tag{4}$$

where x_d be the desired set point and e is the error.

3.2. Twisting Controller

This controller, which was the first 2-sliding controller presented, historically, is the one we'll utilize on our SRM, which is explained below. The formula used to define it is [9].

$$u = -(r_1 \text{sign}(s) + r_2 \text{sign}(\dot{s})), r_1 > r_2 > 0 \tag{5}$$

Figure 03: twisting controller trajectory.

The differential system (equation 2) trajectory converges to the equilibrium point $\dot{s} = \ddot{s} = 0$ in a finite amount of time under the constraints described by the inequalities (4):

$$(r_1 + r_2)K_m - C_0 > (r_1 + r_2)K_M + C_0$$

$$(r_1 + r_2)K_m > C_0 \tag{6}$$

This control law's homogeneity is evident because only its sign, which remains constant when multiplied by $K > 0$, is dependent on the value of s or \dot{s} .

Figure 04: system with twisting algorithm

See [9] for more thorough proofs of this algorithm.

3.3. Design of sliding mode controller

Since first order SMC is notorious for chattering and our machine already has large torque ripple, we won't bother with it for our switching reluctance motor and will instead immediately apply our twisting algorithm to the motor equations for speed control [10]:

For speed regulation we are interested in the dynamics of speed error e , defined as:

$$e(t) = W_{ref} - W \tag{7}$$

When the intended speed, denoted by W_{ref} , is regarded as a known constant. Although the rotor position is a significant element in determining the phase angle θ_p in speed tracking control, we are not interested in regulating it and so treat it as a measured variable. As a result, $\theta_p(t)$ is measured, hence known, function of t .

by replacing $e(t)$ in the general formula of the sliding surface which is defined according to the order of the system as follows:

$$s(x) = \left(\frac{d}{dt} + \gamma\right)^{n-1} e(x) \tag{8}$$

Where n is the system's relative degree in relation to the output $y(t)$. It stands for the minimal number of times that the input must be distinguished from the output $y(t)$ in order for the input to be present there, and the constant γ is positive. Hence, we get:

$$s(x) = \gamma e(t) + \dot{e}(t) \tag{9}$$

Also, we have:

$$\frac{d\theta}{dt} = W$$

$$\frac{dW}{dt} = \frac{1}{J}(T_e - BW - T_L) \tag{10}$$

$$\frac{di_p}{dt} = \left(\frac{\partial \varphi_p(\theta, i_p)}{\partial i_p}\right) \left(u_p - Ri_p - W \frac{\partial \varphi_p(\theta, i_p)}{\partial \theta}\right)$$

$$p = 1,2,3,4$$

Where is:

$$\dot{e} = \dot{W}_{ref} - \dot{W} \tag{11}$$

$$\dot{W}_{ref} = 0$$

So:

$$\dot{e} = \dot{W} = \frac{1}{J} [\sum_{p=1}^4 T_p(\theta_p, i_p) - BW - T_L] \tag{12}$$

In order to realize our twisting controller, we have:

$$\dot{s}(x) = \gamma \dot{e} + \ddot{e} \tag{13}$$

So, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{W} &= \frac{1}{J} \left(\frac{dT_e}{dt} - B \frac{dW}{dt} - \frac{dT_L}{dt} \right) \\ \dot{W} &= \frac{1}{J} \left(\sum_{p=1}^4 \frac{\partial T_p(\theta, i_p)}{\partial \theta} - B\dot{W} - \frac{dT_L}{dt} \right) \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

$$\ddot{W} = \frac{1}{J} \left(\sum_{p=1}^4 \frac{\partial T_p(\theta, i_p)}{\partial i_p} \frac{di_p}{dt} + W \sum_{p=1}^4 \frac{\partial T_p(\theta, i_p)}{\partial \theta} - B\dot{W} - \frac{dT_L}{dt} \right)$$

By replacing i_p :

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{W} &= \frac{1}{J} \left(\sum_{j=1}^3 \frac{\partial T_j(\theta, i_j)}{\partial i_j} \left(\frac{\partial \lambda_j(\theta, i_j)}{\partial i_j} \right)^{-1} \left(-R_j i_j - W \frac{\partial \lambda_j(\theta, i_j)}{\partial \theta} \right) \right. \\ &+ W \sum_{j=1}^3 \frac{\partial T_j(\theta, i_j)}{\partial \theta} - B\dot{W} - \frac{dT_L}{dt} \left. \right) \\ &+ \frac{1}{J} \left(\left(\sum_{j=1}^3 \frac{\partial T_j(\theta, i_j)}{\partial i_j} \left(\frac{\partial \lambda_j(\theta, i_j)}{\partial i_j} \right)^{-1} \right) u_j \right) \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

Now, we replace our sliding surface in equation (5), we get:

$$u = - \left(r_1 \text{sign}(\gamma e + \dot{W}) + r_2 \text{sign}(\gamma \dot{W} + \ddot{e}) \right), \quad r_1 > r_2 > 0 \tag{16}$$

This controller is represented by the diagram below:

Figure 05: SMC-Twisting mode controller for SRM.

4. Simulation, Results and discussions

A numerical simulation was run under the identical test settings to show the improvement provided by the recommended DTC with Twisting controller compared to the variable structures SMC. The various simulation outcomes of the Twisting controller and SMC for SRM are shown in the following figures.

Figure 06: Block diagram of SRM-DTC with twisting sliding mode.

4.1. Results of simulation

We provide three distinct speed references, 1000 tr/min and 1200 tr/min at 0.2 seconds, then 1500tr/min at 0.4 s at the same time a load of 12N.m at 0.3 s in order to demonstrate the strong dynamic response and performance of the 2-SMC.

Figure 07: current (4 phases) and current ripple of one phase.

We observe how smooth the current is compared to other regulation systems. The current peaks at the transit time merely to stabilize at 85A in the steady states and grows at roughly 2 amps after applying a load or altering the speed reference.

Figure 08: Torque of SRM.

The torque is about 5N.m to -1N.m at the permanent regime, when the speed reference is changed, the torque peaks but recovers much faster than in the other tests; once the motor is loaded with 12 N.m, the torque rises to roughly 16 N.m to 12 N.m; note the far reduced torque ripple in this control when compared to PI.

Figure 09: Speed of SRM.

The speed responds to a reference of 1000 tr/min in around 0.005s and after that 1200 tr/min rejecting the steady state perturbation at 3s in a period of time 0.001s, then to follow 1500tr/min and the same response time performing best at both dynamic response and steady state response.

Figure 10: flux linkage of 4 phases and total flux(alfa,beta)

The flux peaks at the transit time just to stabilize at 0.295Wb in the steady state even after loading the motor or changing the speed reference, we note how smoother the flux (on the right side) is Compared to the other regulation techniques.

The total flux linkage has a radius of 0.295Wb and is a perfect circle.

4.2. Robustness Test

It is well known that sliding mode controls are reliable controls, but in order to demonstrate this, we will put our SRM to the test under irrational parametric change scenarios for the purpose of verifying the effectiveness of such a control.

- First robustness test:

The findings of the first test, which uses a parametric change moment of inertia for 0.5 J with orange and 2 J with yellow, results are shown below.

Figure 11: speed for J,0.5J and 2J

We observe that for 0.5J, the response time is around 0.0042 seconds, for 0.005 J and for 2 J, 0.008 seconds. The motor's dynamic response is enhanced by a reduction in moment of inertia, but as the above figure makes abundantly evident, an increase in moment of inertia results in some overshoot during the transient stage.

- Second robustness test:

In this test, we'll adjust the machine's resistance to 0.5 R and with 2 R. The results are shown below:

Figure 12: Speed for 2*Rstator and 0.5*Rstator

We observe that the transit time response is almost the same for 0.5*R, R, and 2*R; the increase or decrease in the coefficient of resistance has no bearing on the dynamic response. Thus, it is clear from the foregoing discussion that the suggested controller is robust to parameter changes and unidentified disturbances. However, the increase had an adverse effect on accuracy, especially for 2*R where the speed has an increase in fluctuation of about 30tr/s and that is not much to notice.

- Third robustness test:

The machine's coefficient of friction will be changed in this test to 0.5B and 2B, and the results are shown below:

Figure 13: Speed for 2*B and 0.5*B

the motor's response when the same friction coefficient modifications are made. The dynamic response is unaffected by the decrements in the coefficient of friction, but is enhanced by the increments in the coefficient of friction.

4.3. Comparing the results between the two speed regulators

We'll give both controllers' findings at the same figure in order to compare them, and then we'll talk about those outcomes.

First the speed of both DTC-PI and DTC-Twisting-SMC:

Figure 14: speed Twisting-SMC/PI controller

The Twisting-SMC/PI performance is shown in the above figure, and it is obvious that the SMC controller outperforms the PI controller in every way when it comes to the speed at which the steady and dynamic states response.

Figure 15: current Twisting-SMC/PI controller

When the peak current of the PI controller, which is 100A, is compared to the peak current of the twisting-SMC, which is 82A, it can be seen that the PI side has significantly more current ripples than the SMC, which is much smoother.

$$Tripple = \frac{T_{max} - T_{min}}{T_{mid}} * 100 = 57\%$$

This table provides a comparison study of the various control strategies.

Table 1: The different the performance of each controller

Torque Ripple	Dynamic Response	Overshoot	Rejection of Disturbance
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DTC with PI	68%	0.05s	22%	0.04s
DTC with Twisting SMC	57%	0.005s	None	0.001s

Both approaches are quick to react, powerful, and robust in the face of disturbances, but TC has a smaller overshoot than PI, and its torque ripple is smaller than the SMC ripple.

5. Conclusion

The design of two nonlinear controllers, such as SMC and TC for SRM, was thoroughly detailed in this study. Conclusion drawn from simulation research comparison: Twisting control can significantly increase the robustness of drive speed regulation. In actuality, the Twisting controller performs admirably in both the rejection of the load's torque and the minimization of the torque ripple caused by chattering.

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